

1 **Coupled carbon and nitrogen losses in response to seven years of chronic warming**
2 **in subarctic soils**

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4 Running title: **Coupled losses of C and N from subarctic soils**

5 Marañón-Jiménez S.^{1,2,3}, Peñuelas J.^{1,2,4}, Richter A.⁵, Sigurdsson B. D.⁶, Fuchslueger, L.³,
6 Leblans N.I.W.³, Janssens I. A.³

7

8 ¹CREAF, Cerdanyola del Vallès, 08193 Barcelona, Spain

9

10 ²CSIC, Global Ecology Unit CREAM-CSIC-UAB, Bellaterra, 08193 Barcelona, Spain

11

12 ³Centre of Excellence PLECO (Plant and Vegetation Ecology), Department of Biology,
13 University of Antwerpen, Campus Drie Eiken, Universiteitsplein 1, C. 203, BE- 2610,
14 Wilrijk, Belgium.

15

16 ⁴Institut d'Estudis Catalans, 08001 Barcelona, Spain

17

18 ⁵Department of Microbiology and Ecosystem Science, University of Vienna,
19 Althanstraße 14, 1090 Wien, Austria

20

21 ⁶Agricultural University of Iceland, Hvanneyri 311, Borgarnes, Iceland

22

23

24

25 ‡Address correspondence to S. Marañón-Jiménez, email: s.maranon@creaf.uab.es

26

27 Research Article

28 **Abstract**

29 Increasing temperatures may alter the stoichiometric demands of soil microbes and impair
30 their capacity to stabilize carbon (C) and retain nitrogen (N), with critical consequences
31 for the soil C and N storage at high latitude soils. Geothermally active areas in Iceland
32 provided wide, continuous and stable gradients of soil temperatures to test this
33 hypothesis. In order to characterize the stoichiometric demands of microbes from these
34 subarctic soils, we incubated soils from ambient temperatures after the factorial addition
35 of C, N and P substrates separately and in combination. In a second experiment, soils that
36 had been exposed to different *in situ* warming intensities (+0, +0.5, +1.8, +3.4, +8.7,
37 +15.9 °C above ambient) for seven years were incubated after the combined addition of
38 C, N and P to evaluate the capacity of soil microbes to store and immobilize C and N at
39 the different warming scenarios. The seven years of chronic soil warming triggered large
40 and proportional soil C and N losses ($4.1 \pm 0.5 \% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ of the stocks in unwarmed soils)
41 from the upper 10 cm of soil, with a predominant depletion of the physically accessible
42 organic substrates that were weakly sorbed in soil minerals up to 8.7 °C warming. Soil
43 microbes met the increasing respiratory demands under conditions of low C accessibility
44 at the expenses of a reduction of the standing biomass in warmer soils. This together with
45 the strict microbial C:N stoichiometric demands also constrained their capacity of N
46 retention, and increased the vulnerability of soil to N losses. Our findings suggest a strong
47 control of microbial physiology and C:N stoichiometric needs on the retention of soil N
48 and on the resilience of soil C stocks from high-latitudes to warming, particularly during
49 periods of vegetation dormancy and low C inputs.

50

51

52 **Keywords:** Substrate induced respiration, microbial biomass, temperature increase,
53 nitrogen immobilization, microbial carbon and nutrients limitation, nitrogen loss

54 **1. Introduction**

55 Global warming is expected to accelerate the decomposition of soil organic matter (SOM)
56 more than its production, causing large releases of CO₂ to the atmosphere and positive
57 feedbacks to the climatic system (Davidson and Janssens et al. 2006, Jenkinson et al.
58 1991). Soils at northern latitudes store more than half of the surface-soil carbon (C)
59 (Tarnocai et al. 2009). As their SOM decomposition has been strongly limited by low
60 temperatures and they are warming more rapidly, they are particularly vulnerable to
61 temperature driven C losses (Smith et al. 2015, Crowther et al. 2016). As such, warming
62 of northern soils may potentially increase global concentrations of atmospheric CO₂
63 (McGuire et al. 2009). Model predictions for future CO₂ emissions and climate change
64 projections by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) remain,
65 nonetheless, largely uncertain (Friedlingstein et al. 2006, Todd-Brown et al. 2013), partly
66 due to the lack of accurate representation of vegetation and soil microbial feedbacks
67 (Bardgett et al. 2013, Friedlingstein et al. 2006) and interactions between C and nutrient
68 cycles (Bradford et al. 2016, Friedlingstein et al. 2006).

69

70 The coupling between C and nitrogen (N) biogeochemical cycles is especially tight in
71 northern ecosystems. Low temperatures constrain the depolymerization and
72 mineralization rates of soil organic N and the release of N-monomers and mineral N, thus
73 limiting plant productivity (Hobbie et al. 2002, Schimel and Bennett 2004, Todd-Brown
74 et al. 2013). Rising temperatures are expected to accelerate the rates of microbial N
75 transformations and alleviate the plant N limitations in these ecosystems, thus increasing
76 plant productivity and C inputs to the soil (Dormann and Woodin 2002, Natali et al. 2012,
77 Wu et al. 2011). Increases in vegetation productivity at warmer temperatures can even
78 offset the soil C losses associated with the accelerated SOM mineralization rates from
79 soil microbes (Melillo et al. 2002, Sistla et al. 2013, IPCC 2013). The vulnerability of soil
80 C stocks to warming will therefore depend on the capacity of soils to retain nutrients and
81 ultimately on the ability of plants to profit from the enhanced nutrient availability.

82

83 Soil microbial biomass plays a fundamental role in the stabilization of soil C (Liang et al.
84 2017, Miltner et al. 2012) and as a short- and long-term N reservoir in soils at high
85 latitudes (Bardgett et al. 2003, Zogg et al. 2000). A large fraction of the N pool in these
86 cold ecosystems is contained in microbial biomass (Jonasson et al. 1996, Xu et al. 2013).
87 This large N storage potential and the low N mineralization rates imply that microbes

88 successfully compete with plants for the limiting N pools during the growing season
89 (Dunn et al. 2006, Skouw Haugwitz et al. 2011), but also that microbial turnover and N
90 release may represent a major pathway for plant N uptake during periods of declining
91 microbial populations (Bardgett et al. 2003). Microbial N retention becomes even more
92 crucial in ecosystems with a period of vegetation dormancy or senescence, such as at high
93 latitudes, when the short photoperiod and low temperatures prevent vegetation
94 productivity and N uptake (Bardgett et al. 2005). Microbial immobilization then becomes
95 a crucial mechanism to minimize potential N losses from the system during relatively
96 long winter periods (Groffman et al. 2011, Jonasson et al. 1996, Kaiser et al. 2011).
97 Warming can, however, desynchronize the intimate seasonal coupling between microbial
98 N immobilization and vegetation uptake in these ecosystems (Bardgett et al. 2005, Jaeger
99 et al. 1999, Lipson et al. 1999), leading to potential soil N and C losses.

100

101 The physiological response of soil microbes to warmer temperatures may elicit shifts in
102 their resource demands, and cause disequilibria on plant-microbial interactions. Although
103 vegetation growth is generally N limited at high latitude ecosystems, C has been found to
104 limit soil microbial growth and biomass even at these high latitudes (Wild et al. 2015).
105 Warmer temperatures may cause persistent increases in microbial respiratory demands
106 and the depletion of the most physically accessible organic substrates in soil (Marañón-
107 Jiménez et al. 2018), thus compromising the C available to maintain constant levels of
108 standing biomass. According to the ecological stoichiometric theory, soil microbes
109 regulate their elemental composition by retaining elements in which they are limited and
110 releasing those in excess (Sterner and Elser 2002). This implies a predominance of
111 microbial N mineralization to N immobilization in strongly C-limited microbes.
112 Warming-induced increases in N mineralization during periods of inactive plant N uptake
113 and accessible C inputs may consequently lead to potential losses of soil N by
114 dissimilatory pathways, either by nitrate leaching or gaseous N fluxes (Turner and Henry
115 2010). Temperature-driven N losses may account for the smaller increase in plant
116 productivity compared to net N mineralization and soil respiration rates frequently
117 observed in experimental warming experiments (Bai et al. 2013, Lu et al. 2013, Rustad
118 et al. 2001), causing divergences between observed and predicted soil C losses for high
119 latitudes (Todd-Brown et al. 2013, McGuire et al. 2018). The potential changes in the
120 capacity of subarctic soils to retain N have not been explored mechanistically yet, even

121 though this information is fundamental to constrain the climate change projections of
122 productivity and soil organic C (SOC) of northern ecosystems.

123

124 Geothermally active areas in Iceland provide stable, continuous and wide gradients of
125 soil temperature (Sigurdsson et al. 2016) that encompass the full range of warming
126 scenarios projected by the IPCC for the northern region (IPCC, 2013). This allow testing
127 for non-linear responses to soil warming and the inference of realistic predictions of soil
128 biogeochemical processes. Previous studies at the same experimental plots from these
129 soil temperature gradients found a linear reduction of 1.28 ± 0.16 ton SOC ha⁻¹ per °C
130 degree of warming from the upper 10 cm of soil (Leblans et al. 2016). Warming increased
131 C losses by accelerating the mass-specific C mineralization rates of soil microorganisms
132 (Marañón-Jiménez et al. 2018, Walker et al. 2018). Surprisingly, enhanced N
133 mineralization in these N-limited soils did not lead to higher vegetation productivity
134 according to the predictions of most ecosystem models (Todd-Brown et al. 2013). On the
135 contrary, aboveground and belowground plant biomass did not change. Vegetation
136 apparently did not benefit from the N released at higher temperatures, probably due to
137 ecosystem N losses. Despite the large and rapid loss of soil C, soil C:N stoichiometry
138 indeed remained unaltered (Leblans et al. 2016), implying a proportional loss of N.

139 In order to assess the mechanisms underlying this coupled soil C and N loss, we incubated
140 soils that had been exposed for seven years to a range of warming intensities in the field
141 due to geothermal activity (0 - 15.9 °C above ambient, hereafter “*in situ* temperatures”).
142 In a first set of soil incubations, the factorial addition of C, N and P substrates separately
143 and in combination to soils from ambient temperatures allowed us to characterize the
144 stoichiometric demands of the microbes from these subarctic soils (hereafter “experiment
145 of stoichiometric demands characterization”). In a second set of soil incubations, the
146 combined addition of C, N and P to the warmed soils along the geothermal gradient
147 allowed us to evaluate the capacity of soil microbes to store and immobilize C and N as
148 affected by different warming scenarios, both at ambient nutrient conditions and when C,
149 N and P are plentiful (hereafter “experiment of warming impacts on soil C and N
150 retention”). Regarding the microbial stoichiometric demands from these subarctic soils,
151 we hypothesized that soil microbes have strong C limitation due to the short growing
152 period for vegetation (low C inputs) and the high clay content of these soils (high physical
153 protection). We also hypothesized that this C limitation and a restricted C:N

154 stoichiometric plasticity of soil microbes limit the immobilization of mineralized N.
155 Regarding the warming impacts on soil C and N retention, the total losses of C from these
156 (Leblans et al. 2016, Poeplau et al. 2016) and many other soils (Hicks Pries et al. 2017,
157 Crowther et al. 2016, Melillo et al. 2017) exposed to warmer temperatures, and the
158 increasing mass-specific respiration rates of soil microbes (Marañón-Jiménez et al. 2018),
159 led us to hypothesize a depletion of the most physically accessible substrates in soil. We
160 also hypothesized that these C scarcity conditions in warmer soils impair the C retention
161 by microbial biomass and the immobilization of the mineralized N that is released from
162 SOM at warmer temperatures. These two complementary experiments will therefore
163 contribute to elucidate the causes of the divergences on the soil C losses between field
164 warming experiments and model predictions at high latitude ecosystems.

165

166 **2. Methods**

167 *2.1. Study site*

168 Soils were collected at the ForHot research site in the Hengil geothermal area, 40 km east
169 of Reykjavik, Iceland (64°00'01"N, 21°11'09"W; 83-168 m a.s.l.), which has been
170 described in detail by Sigurdsson et al. (2016). Mean annual air temperature, annual
171 precipitation and wind speed were 5.2 °C, 1460 mm and 6.6 m s⁻¹, respectively (Synoptic
172 Station, 9 km south of Hveragerdi, Icelandic Meteorological Office, 2016). The mean
173 temperatures of the warmest and coldest months, July and December, were 12.2 and -0.1
174 °C, respectively. The growing season normally starts in late May and ends in late August.
175 Snow cover is not permanent during winter due to the mild oceanic climate, but the soil
176 typically freezes for at least two months during mid-winter. The main vegetation type is
177 unmanaged grassland, dominated by *Agrostis capillaris*, *Ranunculus acris* and *Equisetum*
178 *pratense*, all perennial species with short-lived aboveground parts that regrow each year
179 from underground stems or rhizomes. Sites had been grazed by sheep for centuries (low-
180 intensity grazing), but this practice was ceased in the 1970's (Sigurdsson et al. 2016).

181

182 The soil in the area has been subjected to warming since May 2008 due to geothermal
183 activity, when an earthquake shifted geothermal systems to previously unwarmed soils.
184 Hot groundwater warmed the underlying bedrock and surfaced along faults in the soil
185 crust. Soil temperatures were highest near these faults and declined perpendicular to them.

186 No signs of soil contamination by geothermal byproducts, such as exchangeable sulfur,
187 were found (Sigurdsson et al. 2016). The soils are Andosols with a silty-loamy texture.

188

189 *2.2. Experimental design and soil sampling*

190 Five replicate transects were established in 2012, each covering six levels of *in situ* soil
191 warming: 0, 0.5, 1.8, 3.4, 8.7 and 15.9 °C above ambient (mean annual temperatures in
192 the upper 10 cm of soil). A 0.5 × 0.5 m plot was established for each warming level for
193 soil sampling ($n = 6$ *in situ* temperatures × 5 replicate transects = 30 plots). Soil
194 temperature was monitored hourly at 10 cm soil depth using TidbiT v2 HOBO Data
195 Loggers (Onset Computer Corporation, Bourne, USA). Despite the seasonal and daily
196 oscillations of soil temperatures, the temperature increases above ambient were rather
197 constant along the year and vertically down to ca. 20-25 cm depth (Sigurdsson et al.
198 2016). The mean annual soil temperatures and main soil parameters are indicated in Table
199 1. Plant community composition showed no changes in dominant plant species up to +8.7
200 °C warming (Gudmundsdóttir et al. 2014, Michielsen 2014). At the most extreme
201 warming level (15.9 °C above ambient) the vegetation community shifted towards a
202 higher dominance of non-vascular plants (mosses) (Leblans, personal communication).

203

204 After seven years of soil warming (August 2015), samples from the upper 10 cm of
205 mineral soil were collected from all plots. The mean soil temperature in unwarmed plots
206 two weeks prior to sampling was 11.9 ± 0.3 °C. Soils from each warming level were sieved
207 to 2 mm, mixed and homogenized to constitute a composite sample. The samples were
208 then stored at 5 °C, which is approximately the mean annual temperature of the ambient
209 unwarmed soil, until the analyses and incubations.

210

211 *2.3. Initial soil parameters*

212 Three subsamples of 15, 7.5 and 7 g of fresh soil were extracted with 2 M KCl, 0.5 M
213 NaHCO₃ and 0.5 M K₂SO₄, respectively, within 24 h of sampling. Ammonium (NH₄⁺)
214 and nitrate (NO₃⁻) were determined from the KCl extracts (Bremner and Keeney 1965).
215 Half of the NaHCO₃ and K₂SO₄ extract volume was digested at 400 °C with H₂SO₄ with
216 selenium as a catalyst. Total phosphorus (P) and total extractable N (TN_{K₂SO₄}) were
217 determined from the digested NaHCO₃ and K₂SO₄ extracts, respectively. Available
218 inorganic P (P_{inorg}) was determined from the undigested NaHCO₃ extracts (Olsen et al.
219 1954) and dissolved organic C (DOC_{K₂SO₄}) and NH₄⁺ from the undigested K₂SO₄ extracts.

220 Organic P (P_{org}) and dissolved organic N ($\text{DON}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$) were determined as the difference
221 between digested and undigested NaHCO_3 and K_2SO_4 extracts, respectively (Jones and
222 Willett 2006). Two other pools of soluble organic C were quantified using extractants of
223 different ionic strengths. For this, two subsamples of 10 g of fresh soil were extracted
224 with deionized water ($\text{DOC}_{\text{water}}$), which is a common measure of readily-soluble C, and a
225 weak phosphate buffer at 10 mM (0.33 mM KH_2PO_4 and 6.67 mM Na_2HPO_4) adjusted
226 to pH 7.0 ($\text{DOC}_{\text{buffer}}$), which extracts both the readily-soluble C and weakly adsorbed C
227 in clay minerals (Nelson et al. 1994, Kaiser and Zech 1999). The lower ionic strength and
228 pH of the buffer solution compared to the 0.5 M K_2SO_4 solution reduces the flocculation
229 of organic colloids and the re-adsorption of the solubilized C onto the diffuse double layer
230 surrounding clay particles (Haney et al. 2001). The relative accessibility of extractable
231 soil C pools ($\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$, $\text{DOC}_{\text{water}}$, $\text{DOC}_{\text{buffer}}$) was calculated as the ratio of DOC to SOC
232 pools.

233

234 Another set of subsamples of the same mass of fresh soil were also extracted as described
235 above for determining microbial biomass C and total microbial N and P by fumigation-
236 extraction (Jenkinson and Powlson 1976). Microbial biomass C (C_{micro}), total microbial
237 N (N_{micro}) and total microbial P (P_{micro}) were determined as the difference in $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$,
238 $\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ and total P between the fumigated and unfumigated subsamples, respectively.
239 All analyses were performed by colorimetric detection with a San⁺⁺ Continuous Flow
240 Analyzer (Skalar Analytical B.V., Breda, The Netherlands). NO_3^- was determined after
241 reduction to NO_2^- and formation of the diazo complex at 540 nm wavelength (EN-ISO
242 13395). NH_4^+ was determined after reaction with salicylate, a catalyst and active chlorite
243 solution to form a green colored complex at 660 nm wavelength (ISO 11732). $\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$
244 and NH_4^+ in digested and undigested K_2SO_4 extracts respectively, were determined
245 colorimetrically at 660 nm wavelength. $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ was determined after reaction with
246 phenolphthalein at 550 nm wavelength (ISO 5667-3). P_{inorg} was determined
247 colorimetrically as phospho-molybdic complex at 880 nm wavelength in both digested
248 and undigested extracts (ISO 15681-2). Total soil organic C and total soil N (SOC and
249 TN, respectively) were determined from dry soils by dry combustion at 850 °C with a
250 Thermo Flash 2000 NC Analyser (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Delft, The Netherlands).
251 Inorganic C is not detectible in these volcanic soils (Arnalds 2015), so total C can be
252 considered as organic C. Soil pH was determined by stirring and settling in deionized
253 water in a ratio 1:5 (Pansu and Gautheyrou 2006).

254

255 We calculated the stoichiometric C:N imbalance between soil organic pools and
256 microbial biomass following Mooshammer et al. 2014a, as the ratio of C:N in the SOM
257 pools (SOC:TN and $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}:\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$) over microbial biomass C:N ($C_{\text{micro}}:N_{\text{micro}}$). The
258 C:N imbalance is then a measure of the divergence between the C:N stoichiometry of soil
259 microbes and soil organic substrates, where C:N imbalance < 1 thus reflects a lack of C
260 in SOM pools for soil microbes.

261

262 *2.4. Substrate addition and soil incubation*

263 Subsamples of 40 g (dry equivalent) of fresh soil from the unwarmed ambient plots
264 (hereafter “incubation flasks”) were distributed into flasks within 72 h after sampling. In
265 order to determine the stoichiometric demands of soil microorganisms and their capacity
266 of C storage and N immobilization (experiment of stoichiometric demands
267 characterization), a 1-ml of deionized water solution with a source of C, N, P or their
268 combinations (hereafter “addition”) was added to each flask. We hypothesized that losses
269 of soil N were associated with a restricted capacity of microbial N immobilization, so we
270 tested the effect of two levels of N addition instead of the CP combination. C was added
271 as glucose (1.73 mg of glucose g^{-1} dry soil, that is, 0.69 mg C g^{-1}), N was added as
272 NH_4NO_3 (0.1 mg of NH_4NO_3 g^{-1} , that is, 34 μg N g^{-1} for the N addition level and 0.05 mg
273 of NH_4NO_3 g^{-1} , 17 μg N g^{-1} for the “half-N” addition level) and P was added as KH_2PO_4
274 (0.101 mg KH_2PO_4 g^{-1} , 23 μg P g^{-1}). The amount of substrates added accounted for ca. 1
275 % of the initial soil C content and 0.7 and 0.35 % of the initial soil N content for N and
276 “half-N”, respectively (Table 1). Phosphorous retention is generally >90 % for Icelandic
277 Andosols (Arnalds et al. 1995), so that the P added was ca. ten times the initial available
278 inorganic P soil content to ensure that enough P was accessible to soil microbes. These
279 amounts of substrates were chosen to ensure the alleviation of potential C and nutrient
280 limitations of soil microbes while avoiding potential changes in soil pH. The
281 corresponding combination of the above C, N and P concentrations were used for the CN,
282 NP and CNP addition levels, equivalent to a weight ratio of 20:1:0.67 for the CNP
283 addition level. A set of incubation flasks was also incubated after the addition of 1 ml of
284 deionized water without substrate (hereafter “water-only”).

285

286 The response of microbial biomass to soil warming and the capacity of the warmed soils
287 to retain N in presence of available nutrients (experiment of warming impacts on soil C

288 and N retention) was determined by incubating the samples from each *in situ* warming
289 level with “water-only” and with added C, N and P in combination (CNP) as a single
290 addition level, using the same soil mass and substrate concentrations as above (see
291 Marañón-Jiménez et al. 2018 for further details). Soil moisture was adjusted to 60 %
292 water-holding capacity in all incubation flasks, and the soil was mixed to ensure an even
293 distribution of the solution.

294

295 The soils were then incubated at the mean annual soil temperature in the field (5 °C) and
296 allowed to equilibrate for 12 h. This time lapse was determined in a preliminary assay
297 using the same soils based on the time needed to obtain acceptable coefficients of
298 variability (<20 %) of microbial respiration. Microbial respiration (i.e. substrate induced
299 respiration) was then measured in all samples using an infrared gas analyzer (EGM-
300 4/SRC-1, PP-Systems, Hitchin, UK) coupled to a custom-made chamber with a fan and
301 vent. Incubation flasks were partially closed during the incubation to prevent drying but
302 allow the gas exchange. The flasks were ventilated with a fan for ca. 2 minutes prior each
303 respiration measurement to release the accumulated CO₂ in soil pores and in the air layer
304 closed to the soil surface. Flasks were immersed in a water bath at a constant temperature
305 of 5 °C to maintain the targeted temperature during the respiration measurements.
306 Temperature was continuously monitored during the measurements and incubation using
307 TidbiT v2 HOBO Data Loggers (Onset Computer Corporation, Bourne, USA).
308 Gravimetric soil moisture stayed constant at 60 % water-holding capacity throughout the
309 experiment.

310

311 The incubation temperature of the soil samples was then increased progressively to 30 °C
312 over 6 days (4.6 °C per day) in an incubator with adjustable temperature, allowing us to
313 discard any potential limitation of low incubation temperatures on the microbial substrate
314 uptake and growth (Nedwell 1999). C_{micro} , N_{micro} and the remaining $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$, NH_4^+ and
315 $\text{DON}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ in the soil were determined for all incubated samples as described above six
316 days after the C and nutrient additions to allow soil microbes to take up the substrates.
317 We were only interested in relative differences among treatments, so the concentrations
318 in the microbial fraction presented here were not corrected for extraction efficiency. All
319 fractions are presented relative to soil dry mass.

320

321 *2.5. Data analyses*

322 The effect of *in situ* soil warming on initial soil and microbial C and nutrient contents and
323 ratios prior to the incubations was tested using one-way ANOVAs, and differences among
324 warming levels were further tested by post hoc tests with Tukey correction for multiple
325 testing. The effects of C, N and P substrate additions on microbial respiration, C_{micro} ,
326 N_{micro} , microbial C:N ratios; the remaining $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$, NH_4^+ and $\text{DON}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ and the
327 $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}:\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ ratio in unwarmed soils (experiment of stoichiometric demands
328 characterization) after the incubation were tested using one-way ANOVAs, and
329 differences among addition levels were further tested by post hoc tests with Tukey
330 correction for multiple testing. The differences from soils without any addition were also
331 tested using post hoc Dunnett's tests, using the "water-only" unamended soils as control.
332 The effect of soil warming, substrate addition (C, N and P combined) and their interaction
333 on microbial respiration, C_{micro} , N_{micro} , the microbial C:N ratio (experiment of warming
334 impacts on soil C and N retention) were tested using two-ways ANOVAs, with "addition"
335 and "*in situ* soil warming" as fixed factors. Differences among *in situ* warming levels
336 were further tested by post hoc tests with Tukey correction for multiple testing. The effect
337 of substrate addition on the above variables was also tested for each warming level
338 separately by one-way ANOVAs. Data were transformed when required to improve
339 normality and homoscedasticity (Quinn and Keough, 2009). Stoichiometric ratios were
340 calculated on a mass basis. Statistical analyses and model construction were performed
341 using JMP 13.0 (SAS Institute). All results are presented as means \pm standard errors.

342

343 **3. Results**

344 *3.1. Response of microbial biomass C and respiration of ambient soils to the addition of* 345 *C, N and P*

346 Microbial biomass C (non-corrected for extraction efficiency) constituted only 0.63 % of
347 the SOC in this subarctic soil but contained four times more C than the $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ pool
348 (Table 1). Microbial respiration increased ca. 12 h after the C addition ($P < 0.001$), but N
349 addition and P addition did not cause any significant changes in the rate of microbial
350 respiration (Fig. 1a), either alone or in combination with C.

351

352 Microbial biomass C responded to the additions very similarly to microbial respiration.
353 It increased 29-47 % approximately six days after the addition of a labile C substrate
354 (glucose) (Fig. 1b, $P < 0.001$), while it even decreased in response to the N and P additions

355 alone. Microbial biomass C, however, increased after the combined addition of N and P
356 either alone or in combination with C.

357

358 *3.2. Response of microbial N of ambient soils to the addition of C, N and P*

359 The microbial N pool represented ca. three times the total extractable N in the soil (Table
360 1). Most of this extractable soil N (79 %) was in an organic form, while NH_4^+ and NO_3^-
361 represented only 17 % and 3 % of this pool, respectively (Table 1). Total microbial N
362 only increased significantly in response to the combined addition of C and N (Fig. 2a,
363 $P=0.02$), although values also increased, but not significantly, in all the rest of the addition
364 levels. Consequently, the C addition also caused a depletion of the NH_4^+ in soil (Fig. 2b,
365 $P<0.001$). Circa 82 and 72 % of the NH_4^+ initially available was depleted from the soil
366 when C and N were added in combination in the CN and CNP addition levels, respectively
367 (Fig. 2b), while a large proportion (86, 81 and 111 % for “half-N”, N and NP,
368 respectively) still remained in the soil otherwise. In contrast, soil $\text{DON}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ decreased in
369 response to N-only addition (Fig. 2c, $P=0.007$).

370

371 *3.3. Response of microbial C:N ratios of ambient soils to the addition of C, N and P*

372 The C:N ratios of K_2SO_4 -extractable soil organic substrates decreased to lower values
373 than in microbial biomass after six days of incubation (C:N imbalance <1 , Fig. 3).
374 Microbial C:N ratios increased significantly in response to the CNP addition and
375 decreased after the addition of N and P only ($P<0.001$).

376

377 *3.4. Response of easily accessible soil C pools and C:N ratios to warming*

378 Seven years of continuous warming provoked a substantial depletion of the pools of DOC
379 extracted with K_2SO_4 and with phosphate buffer ($\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ and $\text{DOC}_{\text{buffer}}$, respectively,
380 Fig. 4a), while the most readily-available DOC pool ($\text{DOC}_{\text{water}}$) did not show a consistent
381 decreasing pattern with soil temperatures *in situ*. Moreover, the relative accessibility of
382 the $\text{DOC}_{\text{buffer}}$ pool, calculated as the ratio of $\text{DOC}_{\text{buffer}}$ to SOC pools, decreased with the
383 intensity of soil warming up to 8.7 °C above ambient ($P<0.001$, Fig. 4b), while the relative
384 accessibility of the $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ pool was not substantially affected below this soil warming
385 intensity. Nonetheless, the non-extractable C pools (SOC) were depleted in a higher
386 proportion at the highest warming level (15.9 °C above ambient, Table 1), contributing to
387 increase the relative accessibility of both the $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ and $\text{DOC}_{\text{buffer}}$ pools. The relative
388 accessibility of the $\text{DOC}_{\text{water}}$ pool remained however unaffected by *in situ* soil warming.

389

390 Soil warming also decreased the pools of soil $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ and $\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ proportionally,
391 without any significant shifts in $\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}:\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$ ratios along the *in situ* temperature
392 gradient (Fig. 4c). Even though the C:N ratios of soil organic matter (SOC:TN) were 2.3
393 times higher than the C:N ratios of microbial biomass, the imbalance from the C:N of the
394 extractable fraction of organic substrates ($\text{DOC}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}:\text{TN}_{\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4}$) was initially close to one
395 (Fig. 4c), since the C:N ratios of the extractable organic pools were much lower than the
396 ratios of the total organic matter pools. Warming did not cause shifts in the stoichiometric
397 imbalance between the extractable organic substrates and microbial biomass, given the
398 coupled and proportional losses of C and N from both biomass and soil (Fig. 4c).

399

400 *3.5. Response of soil microbes to warming and to the addition of C, N and P*

401 Despite the depletion of the easily accessible soil C pools, microbial respiration only
402 decreased slightly with *in situ* warming ($P=0.04$, Fig. 5a), and this decrease was only
403 significant at unamended samples (“water-only”, $P=0.03$). *In situ* soil warming however
404 decreased substantially both microbial biomass C and N ($P<0.001$ for both variables),
405 with the largest changes between 1.8 and 3.4 °C above ambient (Fig. 5b, c). Microbial
406 C:N ratios thus did not change significantly with *in situ* soil warming, although variance
407 increased at the warmest soils (Fig. 5d, $P=0.13$).

408

409 The addition of a substrate containing a labile source of C, N and P (CNP) increased
410 microbial respiration in a similar magnitude across all *in situ* warming levels ($P<0.001$
411 for “addition” effect, $P=0.87$ for “addition” and “*in situ* soil warming” interactions, Fig.
412 5a). In contrast, the substrate added increased microbial biomass C only in soils from
413 moderate warming levels <3.4 °C ($P<0.001$, Fig. 5b), but it did not increase at higher
414 warming levels ($P<0.001$ for “addition” and “*in situ* soil warming” interactions), even
415 though the amount of remaining DOC was still higher than in unamended soils ($P<0.01$).
416 Microbial N showed very similar response ($P<0.001$ for “addition” effects, Fig. 5c), but
417 the interaction between “addition” and “*in situ* soil warming” was not significant in this
418 case ($P=0.18$). Microbial C:N ratios, however, did not change substantially in response
419 to the added CNP substrate ($P=0.10$, Fig. 5d), although they tended to increase in response
420 to the addition at *in situ* warming levels ≤ 3.4 °C ($P=0.05$ for “addition” and “*in situ* soil
421 warming” interactions), indicating a proportionally higher retention of C than N.

422

423 **4. Discussion**

424 Nitrogen was lost in the same proportion as C in these subarctic soils (Table 1, Fig. 4c),
425 so that the C:N ratios did not change substantially along the *in situ* soil temperature
426 gradient. This is in contrast to the increase in the availability of soil mineral N and
427 vegetation productivity generally observed in field warming experiments (Dieleman et
428 al. 2012, Dormann and Woodin 2002, Wu et al. 2011). The proportional loss of both
429 elements points to the tight C:N stoichiometric coupling as a mechanism. Soil C losses in
430 response to warmer temperatures have frequently been observed, but experimental results
431 do not always match model predictions for high-latitude ecosystems (Todd-Brown et al.
432 2013, McGuire et al. 2018). Overlooking the relevance of the C and N stoichiometric
433 needs of soil microbes for soils to retain these elements can be a potential cause of these
434 divergences. Soil warming provoked the depletion of a large fraction of the easily
435 accessible C pools in these soils (Fig. 4), where microbial C limitation was already strong
436 (Fig. 1), leading to substantial reductions in microbial biomass and in the capacity of N
437 retention of soil microbes. The strict C and N stoichiometric needs of soil microbes may
438 have determined the coupled losses of C and N from warmed soils, accounting for the
439 constant soil C:N ratios.

440

441 *4.1. C, N and P limitation of microbes in high-latitude soils*

442 Nutrient immobilization by soil microbes can strongly control biogeochemical cycling in
443 ecosystems where temperatures limit the release of nutrients from SOM (Skouw
444 Haugwitz et al. 2011). In these subarctic soils, most of the soil N was in organic form and
445 the microbial N pool represented ca. three times the total extractable N, pointing to the
446 high sensitivity of N biogeochemical fluxes and soil N storage capacity to changes in
447 microbial biomass N. The soils in our incubations have been exposed *in situ* to constant
448 temperature increases relative to ambient temperatures (Sigurdsson et al. 2016), so an
449 increase in mineralization rates and N release to the soil are expected throughout the year.
450 Litter decomposition and mass-specific mineralization rates of the microbes from the
451 same study site were accordingly higher in warmer soils (Leblans et al. 2016, Marañón-
452 Jiménez et al. 2018). The short photoperiod and low temperatures, however, limited
453 vegetation productivity and nutrient uptake during winter dormancy (Leblans et al. 2017).
454 The role of soil microbes in nutrient immobilization for preventing nutrient leaching is

455 therefore crucial during this period, and particularly during winter thaws (Yano et al.
456 2015).

457

458 Soil microorganisms in these subarctic soils were strongly C limited even at ambient
459 temperatures, indicated by a large and equivalent increase in respiration and biomass in
460 response to C addition (Fig. 1). By contrast, microbial respiration was not altered by the
461 N or P additions, and microbial biomass even decreased after the addition of these
462 nutrients alone (Fig 1b). Besides the low vegetation inputs during prolonged winter
463 periods, the strong C limitation can be also partly associated with the low accessibility of
464 most organic substrates, which are sorbed by soil minerals of high specific surface area
465 in these volcanic-ash soils. The large differences between SOC and DOC pools points to
466 a high proportion of non-extractable C strongly occluded (Poeplau et al. 2016). More than
467 ten times organic C was extracted by phosphate buffer than by water in the ambient soils,
468 which also indicates a high proportion of soil C weakly adsorbed to colloidal surfaces
469 (Hayes, 1985). The high adsorption capacity of the fine-textured soils may promote a
470 long-lasting microbial C limitation that, most likely, aggravate in winter, when plant C
471 inputs decrease.

472

473 The relationship between the C:N stoichiometry of soil microorganisms and SOM
474 substrates governs the predominant biogeochemical pathways by which microbes meet
475 their stoichiometric needs using available resources (Mooshammer et al. 2014b).
476 Accordingly, soil microorganisms retain limited elements and release those in excess
477 (Sterner and Elser 2002). The microbial C:N ratios in the soils at ambient temperatures
478 ($C:N=5.41\pm 0.15$, Fig. 4c) were slightly lower than those reported for grassland soils
479 ($C:N=6.6$) and global averages ($C:N=7.6$) (Xu et al. 2013). The SOC:TN ratios of SOM
480 ($C:N=11.97\pm 0.07$) were also lower than for grasslands ($C:N=13.3$) and globally
481 ($C:N=16.4$), and the ratios were even lower in the pool of extractable SOM
482 ($C:N=6.02\pm 0.72$, Fig. 4c). The relatively low microbial C:N ratios in these subarctic soils
483 and a C:N imbalance in relation to the extractable organic pools close to one (Fig. 4c)
484 indicate that N immobilization was not required in large amounts to meet their
485 stoichiometric needs. On the contrary, a net mineralization occurred during the soil
486 incubation in non-amended soils (Fig. 2b), while the immobilization of mineral N was

487 conditioned by the supply of an accessible C pool and the production of new microbial
488 biomass (Figs. 1b and 2).

489

490 Carbon limitation and the strict C:N stoichiometric needs of soil microbes (Zeichmeister-
491 Boltenstern et al. 2015) actually constrained microbial N immobilization. Only the C
492 addition provoked a significant increase in microbial N (Fig. 2a), and N immobilization
493 was highest when C and N were added in combination, although the addition of inorganic
494 N alone also stimulated microbial N immobilization slightly. A 86, 81 and 111 % of the
495 total NH_4^+ initially available still remained in the soil six days after addition for the “half-
496 N”, N and NP addition levels, respectively (Fig. 2b), while only 18 to 28 % remained
497 when C was also added for the CN and CNP additions. The decrease of microbial biomass
498 (Fig. 1b) and the predominant use of DON as C source when only N was added (Fig. 2c)
499 are further evidences of C limitation for microbial growth and N immobilization (Farrell
500 et al. 2014). Similar C constraints of microbial N demands have been observed in Siberia
501 (Wild et al. 2015), reminding the need to frame the concept of C or nutrient limitation to
502 specific ecosystem components or processes rather than generalizing to entire
503 ecosystems. Sub-surface soils (>5 cm depth) also showed no capacity for net retention of
504 increased N inputs after 20 years of fertilization experiment in Alaska, leading to a net C
505 loss (Mack et al. 2004). Soils with relatively low C:N ratios may also present a secondary
506 microbial P limitation. The addition of P in these soils may fuel the synthesis of P-rich
507 mRNA for protein transcription (Elser et al. 1996), enhancing immobilization of soil
508 DON for protein synthesis up to certain level, where the N immobilization is again
509 saturated and limited by C availability (Hessen et al. 2007). This limitation was evidenced
510 by the decrease in microbial biomass in response to the P addition (Fig. 1b). In contrast,
511 the simultaneous supply of N and P needed for protein synthesis may have promoted the
512 allocation of soil organic substrates for microbial growth, resulting in increases in
513 microbial biomass (Fig. 1b). Soils with low C:N ratios where the N storage function of
514 soil microbes is not supported by a continuous supply of easily accessible C will be
515 therefore vulnerable to N losses.

516

517 *4.2. Response of microbial cycling to soil warming*

518 Seven years of continuous soil warming led to a substantial loss of total soil C and N from
519 the upper 10 cm (Table 1), but not all pools of SOC were depleted equally. Both

520 DOC_{K₂SO₄} and DOC_{buffer} pools decreased significantly with *in situ* soil warming, while
521 the DOC_{water} pool did not show a consistent decreasing pattern (Fig. 4a). In relative terms,
522 soil warming provoked a predominant depletion of the DOC_{buffer} pool in relation to the
523 total SOC up to +8.7 °C warming (Fig. 4b), indicating a proportional decrease of the soil
524 organic C adsorbed within the soil minerals. Water-extractable C is known as the most
525 readily-available C pool for soil microbes, but it has also shown a lower biodegradability
526 compared to the buffer-extractable C pool when both pools are fully accessible to soil
527 microbes (Nelson et al. 1994, Wagai and Sollings 2002). Soil microbes may have resorted
528 on the weakly-adsorbed C fraction, the largest DOC pool in these soils, as a predominant
529 C source as the water-extractable C pool was depleted at increasing soil temperatures.
530 Increasing rates of depolymerization and solubilization from the weakly-adsorbed SOM
531 fraction may have also contributed to increase the water-extractable C inputs,
532 compensating the microbial consumption of this pool. Nonetheless, the non-extractable
533 C pools (SOC) also experienced a predominant depletion at the most extreme warming
534 level (15.9 °C above ambient), probably causing a decrease in the surface of organic
535 colloidal surfaces, which contributed to increase the relative accessibility of both the
536 DOC_{K₂SO₄} and DOC_{buffer} pools. Therefore, soil microbes may have satisfied their
537 increasing energy demands at warmer temperatures by a proportionally higher
538 solubilization of the C adsorbed in soil mineral surfaces.

539

540 Microbes increased their respiratory demands per unit of biomass in warmer soils
541 (Marañón-Jiménez et al. 2018, Walker et al. 2018), probably as a consequence of
542 increasing energy costs for metabolic maintenance and for the solubilization of adsorbed
543 organic substrates. Soil warming did, however, not cause substantial shifts in the C:N
544 imbalance between SOM and microbial biomass (Fig. 4c) and the response of respiration
545 to the substrate (C, N and P) addition was also equivalent across warming levels (Fig.
546 5a). Rather than increasing their C demands at the ecosystem level, microbes maintained
547 accelerated rates of C consumption under conditions of low C accessibility by a reduction
548 of the standing biomass (Walker et al. 2018, Fig. 5b), which provoked a coupled and
549 equivalent loss of microbial N (Fig. 5c, d). These results again highlight the strict C:N
550 stoichiometric needs of soil microbes and the tight coupling between N immobilization
551 and biomass production. Warming can therefore lead to proportional soil C and N losses
552 when increased N mineralization rates are not compensated by rapid plant N uptake and
553 plant-derived C inputs to the soil.

554

555 5. Conclusions

556 Seven years of chronic exposure to warmer temperatures led to large and proportional
557 losses of C and N from these high-latitude soils. These findings point to the strict C:N
558 stoichiometric needs of soil microbes and the tight coupling between microbial N
559 immobilization and biomass production as a key mechanism. The continuous exposure
560 of soil microbes to higher temperatures for seven years increased their respiratory
561 demands and provoked the depletion of a large fraction of the easily accessible C pools
562 of these subarctic soils, where microbial C limitation was already strong. Soil warming
563 constrained, as a result, the C retention in microbial biomass and the immobilization of
564 mineralized N. A release of mineral N that is not rapidly compensated by plant N uptake
565 is vulnerable to be lost through leaching in case of nitrification and gaseous fluxes in case
566 of denitrification. The loss of N storage capacity of microbial biomass likely provoked a
567 shift from a close to a leakier N cycle with a detrimental effect on soil N availability and
568 C storage capacity. This mechanism may be key in soils where the low C availability can
569 compromise the maintenance of microbial biomass under a warmer climate, particularly
570 during periods of limited plant C inputs and N uptake. Our results also highlight the need
571 to change the frequent misconception of the ubiquitous N limitation in high latitude
572 ecosystems by a better framed concept of limitation for each specific process or
573 ecosystem component. Accordingly, our findings suggest a strong control of microbial
574 physiology and C:N stoichiometric needs on the retention of soil N and ultimately on the
575 resilience of high-latitude soil C stocks to warming. Overlooking this may be the cause
576 of the large divergences between the predicted response of soil C stocks from models and
577 observations at high latitudes.

578

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595

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812 Figure captions:

813 Figure 1: A) Microbial respiration and B) microbial biomass C in unwarmed soils in
814 response to the C, N and P additions. Microbial respiration was measured 12 h after the
815 additions at the mean annual soil temperature (5 °C). Microbial biomass was measured
816 six days after the substrate additions. Different letters indicate significant differences by
817 Tukey's post hoc tests at $\alpha=0.05$.

818

819 Figure 2: A) Total microbial N, B) remaining NH_4^+ and C) remaining dissolved
820 organic N in unwarmed soils six days after the C, N and P additions. Triangles indicate
821 the initial NH_4^+ concentration in soil prior to the soil incubation. Different letters
822 indicate significant differences by Tukey's post hoc tests at $\alpha=0.05$.

823

824 Figure 3: C:N ratios in A) soil microbes and B) K_2SO_4 -extractable organic pools from
825 unwarmed soils six days after to the C, N and P additions. Different letters indicate
826 significant differences by Tukey's post hoc tests at $\alpha=0.05$.

827

828 Figure 4: A) Dissolved organic C pools, B) their relative accessibility and C) C:N ratios
829 of K_2SO_4 -extractable organic pools, microbial biomass and the C:N imbalance between
830 these at the different intensities of soil warming. Data correspond to the initial values in
831 soils before the incubation or substrates addition. The relative accessibility of extractable
832 soil C pools was calculated as their ratio to the total organic C pool. The C:N imbalance
833 was calculated as the ratio of C:N of soil organic pools over microbial C:N. Different
834 letters indicate significant differences by Tukey's post hoc tests at $\alpha=0.05$.

835

836 Figure 5: A) Microbial respiration, B) microbial biomass C, C) total microbial N and D)
837 microbial C:N ratios in response to the C, N and P addition at the different intensities of
838 soil warming. Microbial respiration was measured 12 h after the additions at the mean
839 annual soil temperature (5 °C). Microbial biomass C and N were measured six days after
840 the additions. Different letters indicate significant differences among the soil warming
841 intensities according to two-way ANOVAs and Tukey's post hoc tests. * and ** indicate
842 significant differences between substrate addition levels within each soil warming
843 intensity according to one-way ANOVAs: $*0.01 < P \leq 0.05$, $**0.001 \leq P \leq 0.01$.